

Collaborative Metadata Definition using Controlled Vocabularies, and Ontologies - FAIR Data Showcase in Experimental Tribology

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The Story

- How to be a Next-gen Research Lab?
 - Preserve Data
 - Accelerate Lab Operations
 - Share Data
 - Run Machine Learning

FAIR Data

Findability

Accessibility

Interoperability

Reusability

■ Communication with Others Researchers

■ **Avoiding Wasting Scientific Resources**

■ Machine-actionable Information

Presentation Outline

Part 1

Proof of Concept (20 minutes)

Tribology:

Friction

Wear

Lubrication

Part 2

Current Framework (20 minutes)

Solutions for Smarter Data

FAIR Data

Findability

Accessibility

Interoperability

Reusability

- Communication with Others Researchers
- **Avoiding Wasting Scientific Resources**
- Machine-actionable Information (e.g. Machine Learning)

■ Limit Scope by **Implementing a “Standard” Showcase Experiment**

- Can Do it *FAIR*'ly?
- What is FAIR for *Tribology*?

**Generating FAIR research data in
experimental tribology**
Nature Scientific Data, 2022

Tribologically FAIR Experiment

Tribologically FAIR Experiment

← → ↻ kadi4mat.iam-cms.kit.edu/collections/15

Kadi4Mat Records Collections Groups Templates Users

Quick search

DOI: TBD

Created at March 9, 2021 4:26:59 PM (9 months ago)
Last modified at December 9, 2021 7:24:16 PM (13 minutes ago)

Created by Nikolay Garabedian

Tags paper publication

Records 45

Advanced search

Optical Surface Profilometry Showcase FAIR Data #0003 scientific procedure

@optical-surface-profilometry-showcase-0003

Scanning a WC-Ni pin's surface after grinding (2D topography raw data). Record based on TriboDataFAI...

Last modified 7 minutes ago

Tactile Surface Profilometry Showcase FAIR Data #0003 scientific procedure

@tactile-surface-profilometry-showcase-0003

Process to acquire 1D profilometric raw data of the WC-Ni pin after grinding. Record based on TriboD...

Last modified 8 minutes ago

Heat Treatment Showcase FAIR Data #0002 industrial procedure

@heat-treatment-showcase-fair-data-0002

Heat treatment of 100Cr6 discs to increase toughness. Heating: Furnace was pre-heated to 190 °C. Tem...

Last modified 3 days ago

Block Specimen YUL-MSE-006 experimental object

@block-specimen-yul-mse-006

A disc shaped sample made from 100Cr6 bearing steel. Record based on TriboDataFAIR-Ontology URL: htt...

Last modified 3 days ago

Specimen Cleaning Showcase FAIR Data #0004 industrial procedure

@specimen-cleaning-showcase-fair-data-0004

Cleaning procedure to remove residue after wet cup grinding. Record based on TriboDataFAIR-Ontology ...

Last modified 3 days ago

Heat Treatment Showcase FAIR Data #0001 industrial procedure

@heat-treatment-showcase-fair-data-0001

Heat treatment of 100Cr6 discs to increase hardness. Heating: Furnace was pre-heated to 860°C. Tempe...

Last modified 5 days ago

Page 1 of 8

Filter

Record Experimental Tribological Data (*Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability*)

- Main page
- Instructions
- To-Do Hub
- Information recorded in time series
- Recent changes
- Random page
- Help
- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Upload file
- Special pages
- Printable version
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Browse properties

Main Page

This is an attempt to use a Wiki to work on and eventually define a (internal) meta-

New users — to get started and learn how to contribute to the project, you can go to the

Experienced users — this link takes you to the **Work in Progress Hub**.

Overview [\[edit\]](#)

On the following wiki-pages we try to collect necessary terms (the vocabulary) to prop-

Metadata [\[edit\]](#)

▼ Object

- General Vocabulary:Metadata/002 Tribometer*
- General Vocabulary:Metadata/004 Tribological sample*
- General Vocabulary:Metadata/005 Interfacial medium for tribological experiments*
- General Vocabulary:Metadata/007 Band saw*
- General Vocabulary:Metadata/008 Furnace*
- General Vocabulary:Metadata/009 Cup grinding machine*
- General Vocabulary:Metadata/010 Tactile surface profilometer*
- General Vocabulary:Metadata/011 Optical surface profilometer*
- General Vocabulary:Metadata/012 Demagnetizing plate*
- General Vocabulary:Metadata/013 Ultrasonic cleaner*
- General Vocabulary:Metadata/020 Hardness tester*

▼ Process

- General Vocabulary:Metadata/001 Tribological experiment*
- General Vocabulary:Metadata/006 Sample cleaning*
- General Vocabulary:Metadata/014 Sawing*

Record Experimental Tribological Data (*Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability*)

Ontology vs. Controlled Vocabulary

a. Free-Text Description

"The tests were performed on a CSEM tribometer at room temperature (20.7° C) and a low viscous automotive Shell V-Oil1404 was applied."

Ontology

Kadi4Mat

Controlled
Vocabulary

Record Experimental Tribological Data FAIR'ly

(*Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability*)

Record Experimental Tribological Data FAIR'ly

(*Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability*)

Data Availability

zenodo

Search

Q

Upload

Communities

Log in

Sign up

November 23, 2021

Dataset

Open Access

FAIR Data Package of a Tribological Showcase Pin-on-Disk Experiment

 Garabedian, Nikolay; Schreiber, Paul; Li, Yulong; Blatter, Ines; Dollmann, Antje; Haug, Christian; Kümmel, Daniel; Meyer, Franziska; Morstein, Carina; Rau, Julia; Greiner, Christian

To assess the feasibility of producing FAIR data via the integration of a controlled vocabulary, an ontology, and an ELN, this dataset demonstrates the implementation of a tribological experiment while accounting for as many details as possible. The showcase experiment had a lubricated pin-on-disk arrangement, ran at 15 N normal load and a velocity range of 20 to 170 mm/s. With this dataset, we hope to provide a possible blueprint for FAIR data publication in experimental tribology.

This dataset is associated with a publication (soon to be linked here) detailing its purpose and explaining its contents.

Preview

 FAIR Tribological Data of Showcase Pin-on-Disk Experiment.zip

 FAIR Tribological Data of Showcase Pin-on-Disk Experiment

 block-specimen-100cr6-rod-001

- block-specimen-100cr6-rod-001.json 9.5 kB
- block-specimen-100cr6-rod-001.pdf 76.8 kB
- files
- 2_1_8_100cr6_delivery_00087022.jpg 641.0 kB
- 2_1_8_100cr6_delivery_00087022.txt 635 Bytes
- 2_1_8_100cr6_delivery_00087023.jpg 524.4 kB
- 2_1_8_100cr6_delivery_00087023.txt 637 Bytes
- 2_1_8_100cr6_delivery_00087024.jpg 423.6 kB
- 2_1_8_100cr6_delivery_00087024.txt 637 Bytes

106

views

20

downloads

[See more details...](#)

Indexed in

Publication date:

November 23, 2021

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Related identifiers:

Cites

[10.5281/zenodo.5720198](#) (Other)

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Tribological Data FAIR'ly

From Showcase to Business-as-Usual

Proof-of-Concept

Make FAIR a daily way of conducting science

- Limit S
- Can Do it FAIR'ly?
- What is FAIR for Tribology?

ML

FAIR

Reliable

Electronic Lab Notebook

herbie

Kadi⁴Mat

Chemotion

+ more

Open

Open Repository

+ more

↕ **FAIR-Save**

FS-DigitalBook

FS-Validator

FS-Analysis

+ more

FS-Instrument

+ more

FAIR

Electronic Lab Notebook

herbie

Kadi⁴Mat

Chemotion

+ more

Open

Open Repository

+ more

List terms New term

Available terms

Vocabulary Graph

- Block Specimen approved
- General Info approved type: dictionary
- Location not approved type: dictionary
- Operator in Charge not approved type: dictionary
 - First Name not approved type: string
 - Last Name not approved type: string

Label: Block Specimen

Definition: Objects of this class contain a self-bound collection of mass bearing particles. Block speci

Synonyms (with language tags):

Data type:

Relatively broader terms:

Relatively narrower terms:

Related terms (non-hierarchical):

- Ultrasonic Cleaner

2 1

 [Ilia Bagov @qq6915](#) Updated on 2022-05-17 at 14:46
Looks good.

 [nick-garabedian @nick-garabedian](#) Updated on 2022-05-18 at 18:48
I like it.

Add a new comment:

System for Controlled Vocabularies

VocPopuli Features

Part 1

Part 2

List terms

New term

Import vocabulary

Choose a vocabulary project: ▾

Select

[Login with GitLab](#)

VocPopuli Under the Hood: Term Creation

time →

Vocabulary:
Cup Grinding

VocPopuli Under the Hood: Term Creation

VocPopuli Under the Hood Features:

- Git-based tracking
 - Who?
 - When?
- PROV-DM data model
- SKOS ontology

Electronic Lab Notebook

herbie

Kadi⁴Mat

Chemotion

X W

+ more

Open Repository

zenodo

+ more

Vocabulary Management Tool

■ Controlled Vocabulary (in VocPopuli)

The screenshot shows the VocPopuli web interface. The header includes the logo, navigation links for "List terms", "New term", and "Import vocabulary", and a user profile icon. The main content area is titled "Available terms" and displays a list of terms with their approval status. A blue box highlights the "Populi" logo and a "semi-supervised" arrow pointing to the right.

Term	approved	unread
Ultras...		
Specin...		
Spec...		
Gene...		
Op...		
Location Information	approved	unread
Room Number	approved	unread
Institution (Location)	approved	unread
123 Floor	approved	unread
Building	approved	unread

■ Ontology (TriboDataFAIR)

Karlsruhe Lab Framework

Part 1

Part 2

ML

FAIR

Reliable

Electronic Lab Notebook **herbie**

+ more

Open

Open Repository

+ more

FAIR-Save

FS-DigitalBook

FS-Validator

FS-Analysis

+ more

FS-Instrument

+ any other

VocPopuli Summary

- **Collaborative FAIR** vocabulary management
- Entry point to digitalization (on individual level)
- A step towards scalable machine learning

Current Affairs (Results)

- How long to see the tribological results after an experiment?

- ~ 2 minutes

- Immediate Returns:

- A Recent Accident and Calibration Check*

- How long do it take **us** to set up?

- > 2 years

- How long will it take **others** to set up?

- Highly variable:

- From HOURS to WEEKS to MONTHS (goal dependent)*

Is it worth it?
Absolutely!

Speaker: Nick Garabedian

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(1) Showcase Implementation

(2) Production-Ready Implementation

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